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Work Package 10

Secure Infrastructure for big data

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Project Deliverable

**D10.3 - Report describing implementation and experiences
from HEAP research use cases**

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Executive Summary

This report builds on the D10.2 deliverable of HEAP that was focused on *Documentation of the secure data platform and its integration* and illustrates some of the experiences from HEAP-specific research use cases in relationship with the secure data platform. This deliverable recognises the use cases relevant to the HEAP researchers and details the steps taken to support them.

This report records the efforts coordinated within the Secure Infrastructure for Big Data Work Package (WP10) and its goal to develop a secure workspace to facilitate sensitive data usage through the HEAP Information Commons as well as enabling the analysis of data through the Hopsworks software (WP6) to support research use case derived from HEAP cohorts and driven by WP3, WP5 as well as other work packages.

At the same time, this report depicts how HEAP research use cases can make use of CSC Sensitive Data Services and Hopsworks in order to get consent for the data as well as to analyse it in a secure environment.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The activities of Work Package 10 focused mainly on developing an IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) secure data platform suitable for managing sensitive data.

As WP10 continued the work plan established in the D10.1 focusing both on the short-term goals as well as long-term goals, the effort gravitated towards finalising the structure of the HEAP components, interfaces, and standards to be utilised and as well as identifying interoperability end-points between components detailed in the HEAP Reference Architecture.

1.2 Overview

This builds on the same tasks that stood at the basis of the D10.2 report, namely:

- Task 10.2 Development of sensitive data management platform
- Task 10.3 Dataset authorisation and access
- Task 10.4 Secure data access from institutional repositories
- Task 10.5 Support research use cases

Progress on these tasks was made incrementally. In the first reporting period, SD Connect (part of Submission Engine and Information Commons) and SD Desktop services were launched, whilst, in the 2nd reporting period, new functionalities were developed for these services (Task 10.2). In the third reporting period, two new services have been piloted for the secure data platform development: SD Submit (a service aimed at publishing data under controlled access; part of Information Commons and Task 10.4) and SD Apply (Entitlements Management System).

At the same time, in the third reporting period, a plan was first established for integrating Hopsworks software (Knowledge Engine, WP6) with the secure infrastructure mentioned in the D6.1 deliverable (Task 10.2) as presented in D10.2 and implementation towards achieving the set plan is ongoing. The integration endpoint, identified via the CSC Data Gateway software, was provided to secure access to data stored in SD Connect and SD Submit services (Task 10.3).

As specified in the previous deliverable, the *D10.3 Report describing implementation and experiences from HEAP research use cases* - reviews some of the means through which researchers perform their analysis and use the secure data infrastructure and the cohorts in the "Information Commons".

The work presented in this current report also contributes towards achieving *Milestone 5 Population of the "Information Commons"*. Although this milestone could not be achieved by the set deadline, as most of the work required to fulfil it is ongoing, three datasets (that require a persistent identifier) have been successfully ingested into the CSC SD Services and are available for the HEAP researchers via SD Apply catalogue¹ or Fairdata² IDA storage.

- WP3: *Synthetic HPV vaccination data*
<https://doi.org/10.24340/vqcx-3fbj6h>
- WP3: *Longitudinal metagenome data*
<https://doi.org/10.24340/dg5u-gapqxn>
- WP3: HPV Aggregated clinical data
<https://doi.org/10.24340/mxdt-m377>

Other data specific to the HEAP Population of "Information Commons" that does not require a persistent identifier - data in active use is available through SD Connect in the HEAP platform. Such data is managed through individual CSC projects³ by WP3 and WP5.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The structure of the document is as follows:

- Chapter 1 - (this chapter) introduces the document and its purpose concerning the HEAP project.
- Chapter 2 - reiterates some of the HEAP use cases identified by D10.1
- Chapter 3 - describes the implementation of the identified use cases and the challenges faced
- Chapter 4 - provides a summary of the current report and bridges towards the final deliverable of the WP10, namely D10.4

2. Reviewing HEAP Use Cases

¹ <https://sd-apply.csc.fi/catalogue>

² <https://www.fairdata.fi/en/ida/>

³ <https://docs.csc.fi/accounts/>

Table 1 below summarises the Use cases identified via the Reference architecture survey in deliverable D10.1. From this table, we identified that UC2, UC3 and UC4 were the main drivers for WP10's sensitive data infrastructure and building up the Information Commons.

	Use Case	Use case description
UC1	The cohorts are managed in a more efficient way and linked to a metadata search engine (e.g., Maternity cohort and HPV vaccination cohort)	Use a metadata search engine to make data more accessible and easier to find via a metadata search engine.
UC2	Analyse available sequence data from different data sources (e.g. Cervical screening cohort, Sweden, and from the US public database)	Analyse for the presence of all exposures (viral, bacteria, others) using existing bioinformatics pipelines developed and use them in the HEAP platform installed at partner nodes (e.g. CSC, KI).
UC3	Consumer cohort data analysis	Use IC as a storage engine to work/combine with other data - e.g. Analysis of consumer data determinants of health and diseases.
UC4	Investigations on best exploring the advantages of Hopsworks	Pilot retrieving data archived in IC for analysis and/or processing from Knowledge Engine (Hopsworks).

Table 1. Use cases identified as per Reference Architecture survey D10.1.

In the initial use case analysis for the HEAP project, we identified the following requirements:

- **RQ1:** Compare sequence data to existing microbe sequence data and perform large-scale metagenome analysis (such as assembly, classification network analysis, etc);
- **RQ2:** Enable controlled data access, as some datasets require traceability of the data usage purpose or if data can or cannot be transferred across country borders (or is behind a firewall);
- **RQ3:** Enable large-scale metagenome analysis and inference in computational environments (HPC) that support parallelisation;
- **RQ4:** Provide support for plotting and visualising across datasets;
- **RQ5:** Work heterogeneous and distributed datasets;
- **RQ6:** Manage and make the data findable and accessible.

In the context for WP10 (see Table 3 from D10.1), RQ2, RQ3, RQ4, and RQ4 were the main drivers for the work on Information Commons, whilst RQ2, RQ5, and RQ6 steered the integration with the Entitlements Management System.

2.1 Discerning between Use Cases

As we noted in D10.1, the requirements identified in Table 1 do not represent the full set of requirements of the HEAP Reference Architecture for the sensitive data infrastructure. We can refine how to best support the HEAP use cases by understanding the types of data the researchers use or identifying the steps to publish and access the data.

As pointed out in D10.2, we can distinguish two types of data that will be stored in Information Commons:

1. *work data* or *data in active use* - (e.g. raw anonymised, stream) data represents the most frequent type of data used in computations, e.g. through the HEAP Knowledge Engine pipelines to derive insights.
2. *published data* - depicts data identifiable via a permanent identifier (such as a DOI (Document Object Identifier) [3]) that researchers can use in their publications for reference purposes. However, this data can be used to derive insights in combination with other work, publish data, or even both. This type of data might require controlled access under the supervision of a Data Access Committee (e.g. HEAP Entitlements Management System).

At the same time, another perspective is provided by the process through which research is performed:

1. Active phase - which consists of data collection and data analysis. Based on the data classification, analysing the data might require a Sensitive Processing Environment [4]
2. Dissemination phase - communicating the results to an audience, which usually implies the data is provided via a persistent identifier for reproducibility purposes. Depending on the data classification, this might require, as the published data type mentioned previously, the supervision of a Data Access Committee.

Indifferent of the perspective we use to ascertain the use case we are tackling, international collaboration is an integral part of supporting HEAP research use cases, either by enabling federated computation or just

providing a common way to access the data, i.e. through an AAI, such as LifeScience AAI⁴.

At the same time, data sharing, regardless of the phase or type, should be possible. For example, in the active phase, other researchers can be involved by just providing a subset of the initial data or enabling them to provide other data streams.

3. Use Cases Implementation

This chapter focuses on active and dissemination phases to describe the use case implementation, as deliverable D10.2 presented the implementation from the active data and publishing data perspective in Chapter 4 of the report.

Figure 1. Authorisation Workflow for users Accessing Hopsworks inside SD Desktop (source D10.2)

Figure 1 illustrates how integration between CSC SD Services and the Hopsworks software is achieved to deliver on the HEAP Reference Architecture.

⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/compute/aai/overview>

For the definitions and technical description of the CSC SD services described in this chapter, refer to the D10.2 deliverable chapters 2 and 3.

3.1 Active Phase

All these services use CSC accounts and access to resources that have the concept of a project at their base. Such projects are used to manage access to CSC services and the resources provided by CSC.

Each CSC project can be viewed as an individual research use case which includes one or several CSC user accounts, with the feature that one user account can be a member of several projects. A project must have a Project Manager, typically a leader of a research team or other senior researcher, who creates the project, manages the user accounts and services that belong to the project and is responsible for resource usage.

In the active phase of the research, we identified that there are needs for submitting (Submission Engine) and storing data (Information Commons) as well as providing a secure environment where researchers can perform analysis on set data using predefined or custom pipelines (Knowledge Engine).

In the context of the HEAP WP10 identified the necessary CSC SD services infrastructure to support this phase, namely:

- SD Connect, which is developed on top of the CSC object storage service (Allas⁵), provides a user interface for submitting encrypted data and sharing data with other researchers in the same or different projects. At the same time, it can be used to facilitate data sharing between research projects. There are three levels of sharing across CSC projects via SD Connect⁶: *no permissions*, *read permissions*, and *read-write permissions*. Enabling such data-sharing functionality allows researchers to collaborate with other research groups while maintaining control over their data during the active phase. Another functionality identified by the research use cases, derived from WP3, is the capability to tag the data in the submission interface, allowing researchers to easily filter and identify the data stored in each SD Connect project they are part of.
- SD Desktop⁷ represents a sensitive processing environment. It is a service aimed towards analysing sensitive research data, built on top of ePouta, providing an isolated, secure private cloud computing

⁵ <https://docs.csc.fi/data/Allas/>

⁶ <https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd-connect-upload-for-storage-and-sharing/#data-sharing>

⁷ User Documentation for SD Desktop https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/sd_desktop/

environment accessible via a remote desktop. In the context of HEAP, SD Desktop service comes as a solution for providing restricted access to the HEAP Knowledge Engine deployed on the secure data platform. The integration between the SD desktop and the Knowledge engine is described in D10.2 and is still ongoing. By achieving this integration, we aim to provide a way for researchers to analyse their data and run the necessary pipelines (WP6 and WP3).

Another part of the active phase consists of exporting results from a secure processing environment. In the case of using SD Desktop services, the CSC project manager must do this to provide a certain level of accountability for the exported data.

3.2 Dissemination Phase

For the dissemination use case, we can provide another dimension based on the data classification:

- Synthetic Data - test data sets of production or operational data that aim to test analysis pipelines that require a persistent identifier. Such data does not require persistent identifiers; however, it does not require control access.
- Sensitive Data - depending on the HEAP cohort, this can range from data that contains health, genetic, environmental, and personal information that may identify a person, requires a persistent identifier, and is under controlled access.

To fulfil this phase in WP10, we identified the following CSC Services that we can utilise:

- Fairdata IDA⁸ - research data storage offered to Finnish universities, universities of applied sciences and state research institutes. We can use IDA to save, organise and share data within a CSC project group and store it in an immutable state before the data is described as a research dataset with the Fairdata Qvain tool. The described data can be set openly available with Fairdata Qvain⁹. The research dataset published with Qvain gets a persistent identifier and a landing page in Etsin¹⁰.
- SD Submit - is a service similar to Fairdata IDA. However, it is geared towards sensitive data, and it provides the necessary workflows to facilitate collecting metadata descriptions for user-provided datasets and streamlines data distribution and reuse. It registers submitted

⁸ <https://www.fairdata.fi/en/ida/>

⁹ <https://www.fairdata.fi/en/qvain/>

¹⁰ <https://www.fairdata.fi/en/etsin/>

data with the data access committee so that it will stay in control of this data. At the same time, the service provides a permanent identifier (DOI) so that the data can be persistently identified and made findable through services such as Etsin.

- Federated European Genome-phenome Archive (FEGA) [5] - was developed to store and publish personally identifiable genetic and phenotypic data given with consent for research but not for full public dissemination. The federation consists of national nodes across the European Union and elsewhere, working together with the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA). In the context of the HEAP project, this means that HEAP researchers would have access to data on a European level, data which they can use in their research, thus facilitating federated analysis. Since the previous report, the FEGA service has become operational at CSC and accepts submissions. The implementation of this service is based on the NeIC Sensitive Data Archive¹¹ suite of services.
- SD Apply - represents a service for data controllers to manage data access permissions on their datasets stored as part of the Federated European Genome-phenome Archive (FEGA) or SD Submit. SD Apply makes the data access application process fully electronic by recording all access decisions, documents, and provided information in the process, and the logs can be used to build reports or as part of audit tracks.

The integration of the CSC (SD) Services and their workflow was presented in D10.2 chapters 3 and 4.

3.3 HEAP platform governance

Deliverable D2.3 bring forward four use cases from a platform governance viewpoint:

- *Use case 1: HEAP platform deployed for one individual research group:* The HEAP platform can be deployed in the research group's internal IT resources (server, computer cluster, storage)
- *Use case 2: HEAP platform deployed inside one institution's boundaries* - It refers to several research groups from the same institution sharing the HEAP platform. The HEAP platform is deployed in a shareable institutional IT resource (virtual server, computer cluster, HPC, etc.)

¹¹ <https://neic-sda.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

- *Use case 3: HEAP platform deployed for cross-institutional research* - The HEAP platform is deployed in a shareable IT resource provider (cloud, HPC, etc.)
- *Use case 4: HEAP platform deployed for cross-border research* - The HEAP platform is deployed in a shareable IT resource provider (cloud, HPC, etc.)

With the implementation provided by WP10, based on CSC SD Services, we aim to fulfil Use Cases 3 and 4 as described by Deliverable D2.3. For use case 4, using an existing federated initiative such as the Federated EGA as a starting point for supporting cross-border research is relevant.

4. Summary

The main goal of this report is to provide the implementation progress based on the HEAP research use cases. It achieves this by defining some of the identified research use cases and how the HEAP components help fulfil them. The report also highlights, in particular, the use cases and their relationship with CSC SD Services and the Hopsworks software, which are key components of the platform. The implementation details have been presented in D10.2, and this report references those particular details. This report does not go into the implementation details as this is still in progress, together with onboarding the data related to the cohorts.

4.1 Achievements and Future Plans

The current report encompasses the experiences of supporting HEAP research use cases as part of WP10, alignment with HEAP Informatics Platform and Knowledge Engine (WP6), and HEAP Data Management Plan (WP7). It considers the steps necessary to support HEAP use cases from the different cohorts, e.g. WP3 Large Sample Cohorts from Population-Based Interventions and WP5 Exposome Monitoring and Metabolomics Profiling.

This work from this deliverable, together with the previous deliverable, builds up to the final report on:

- D10.4 Report on the security measures that have been implemented to prevent unauthorised access to personal data or the equipment used for processing.

5. References

1. D10.1: Reference Architecture - HEAP report June 2020
2. D10.2 - Documentation of the secure data platform and its integration into HEAP - HEAP report June 2023
3. Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Accessed December 20 2023, <https://www.doi.org/>
4. Data Governance Act (DGA) - EU regulation 2022/868, Accessed December 20 2023, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32022R0868>
5. Federated EGA at EGA Archive website, Accessed December 20 2023, <https://ega-archive.org/about/projects-and-funders/federated-ega/>